

AstraFund

A Smart and Secure
Crowdfunding Platform
Powered by Blockchain and AI

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Objective

Design a secure AI-driven blockchain-based crowdfunding platform that predicts campaign risk before funding and detects fraudulent activities during transactions in real time.

Problem:

- High campaign failure risk
- Fraudulent transactions
- Lack of trust

Solution Structure:

Entrepreneur

AI Risk Prediction Model (Before Funding)

Blockchain Secure Transaction Layer

Investor

During Funding

Anomaly Detection Model

Fraud Alert System

A secure crowdfunding platform connecting Admin, Investors, and Entrepreneurs.

Uses Blockchain for secure transactions and AI for dynamic project evaluation.

Enhances trust, ensures transparency, and minimizes investment risks.

System Overview

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Entrepreneur submits campaign details

AI Risk Prediction Model evaluates campaign success probability

Risk score generated before funding

Blockchain smart contract created for secure transactions

Investors fund the campaign

Anomaly Detection Model monitors transactions in real time

Fraud alert triggered if abnormal behavior is detected

Fund Aura

PROJECT GOALS

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Enhance trust and
transparencys

Reduce investment
risk using AI

Detect fraudulent
transactions in real
time

Secure financial
operations using
blockchain

AI Model :

Risk Prediction Models:

- **XGBoost**
- **Random Forest**
- **Logistic Regression**
- **Gradient Boosting**

Used to estimate campaign success probability before funding.

Anomaly Detection:

- **Isolation Forest**
- **SVM**
- **Autoencoder**

Used to detect abnormal transaction behavior in real time.

Overfitting

Occurs when the model learns noise instead of general patterns.

Prevention:

Data splitting

Cross-validation

Regularization

Balanced dataset

DATASET

Dataset 1:

Kickstarter Projects Dataset

Source: Kaggle
Features: Goal, Category, Duration, Backers, Funding Outcome
Used for Risk Prediction

Dataset 2

Synthetic User Behavior Dataset

Simulated transaction behaviors
Normal vs Fraud scenarios
Used for Anomaly Detection

Data Handling

- **70% Training**
- **15% Validation**
- **15% Testing**
- **Cross-validation applied to reduce overfitting**

State of the Art

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Paper	Dataset	Methods	Features	Accuracy
Greenberg et al., 2013 [1]	Kickstarter	Logistic Regression	Goal, Duration, Category	68%
Xu et al., 2016 [2]	Kickstarter	Random Forest	Text + Funding data	74%
Li et al., 2020 [3]	Financial Fraud Dataset	Isolation Forest	Transaction behavior	92%
Chen et al., 2022 [4]	Blockchain Finance Dataset	XGBoost	Hybrid financial features	89%

Accuracy comparison must be interpreted carefully due to differences in datasets and evaluation metrics

Tools and Technologies

POST

BLOCK DIAGRAM

USECASE DIAGRAM

ERD DIAGRAM

DIFFICULTIES

01

Human Factor
and Fraud

02

Electronic Payment
Platforms

03

Geographical
Location and
Proxy/VPN Usage

REFERENCE IEE

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- [2] A. Xu, X. Yang, H. Rao, W. Fu, S. Huang, and B. Bailey, “Show Me the Money! An Analysis of Project Updates during Crowdfunding Campaigns,” in Proc. ACM Conf. Computer-Supported Cooperative Work (CSCW), 2016, pp. 591–600.
- [3] F. T. Liu, K. M. Ting, and Z.-H. Zhou, “Isolation Forest,” in Proc. IEEE Int. Conf. Data Mining (ICDM), 2008, pp. 413–422.
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THANK
YOU

